

Jaina Antiquities from Tatgram, Purulia District (West Bengal)

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Introduction:

From the very beginning of civilization, rivers played an important role in the growth and development of the human settlements. The western part of West Bengal, mostly covered by the extension of the Chhotanagpur plateau, is the playground of rivers like Mayurakashi, Ajay, Damodar, and Kansavati. These rivers also played a prominent role in the expansion of settlements in this region. Similarly, the small and seasonal rivers like Dwakashwar, Silabati, Kumari, Harai also played crucial role in the settlement history of this area and during the recent extensive exploration programme it was possible to successfully record both Jaina and Brahmanical remains from large number of villages along these seasonal rivers.

Archaeologically, Para is one of the important blocks in the Purulia district which helps in reconstructing the early medieval archaeological profile of the district in general. In the last three to four years, authors have extensively explored this block and able to document dozens of archaeological sites. Among these sites some are already reported and few are newly documented.

The site **Para** itself is one of the important archaeological sites in this district. The site is located at a distance of about 20 km from Purulia town on the eastern bank of the river Harai. On a low mound at the center of the village are two temples, of which one is carved of stone and another is brick-built. 500m. away from is a dilapidated temple constructed with brick and stone known as Raghunath temple. J.D.Beglar first reported this site and documented in details. He

reported the presence of several sculptural specimens including a solitary piece of hero-stone, at present this is unnoticeable. He also mentioned about the presence of four temples at the site in different stage of preservation (Beglar 1878/1966: 162-169). In 1903 T. Bloch also visited this site and saw a much mutilated ‘Lakshmi’ image in the stone temple while the brick temple in his time contained ‘an image of Durga with ten arms (Bloch 1903:15). Chakrabarti reported seeing a *lingam*, a Nataraja medallion, an Uma-Mahesvara image and an unidentified female figure besides several other mutilated sculptural specimens in the brick temple now known as Chandimandir (Chakrabarti1993: 127). Another sacred spot in the village known as Yamraj *sthan* contains a mutilated specimen of a Vishnu image. Intensive survey at each and every locale in the village made it clear that besides its Brahmanical character, the site also possesses ample evidence of Jaina religious ethos. In the Raghunath temple, the fragmentary piece of the feet of a Tirthankara and another specimen of a tree with a depiction of a figure in its branching part clearly authenticate the above statement. Besides, administrative records also shed light on the presence of a sizable population of Jain communities still occupying a considerable portion of the site and its nearby area.

The present study mainly promises to highlight the following issues: 1) to briefly discuss the iconographic details of the newly documented sculptural remains from Tatgram, a newly reported archaeological site; 2) to discuss about the archaeological potentiality of the newly identified archaeological site/settlement; 3) try to emphasis on the logical uses of the memorial stones reported from this site and 4)to search for logical explanations behind the presence of Brhamanical sculptural material in an otherwise Jaina milieu.

Tatgram and its Archaeological remains

Location of the village between the two seasonal rivers Harai and Gorai flowing along the two sides of this village presents a beautiful landscape. The village is situated about 19 km north - west of Para and 7 km east of Chandankiyari –an important archaeological site in Jharkhand. The site Tatgram is full of archaeological wealth and interestingly during our recent visit at this site we discovered few Black-and-Red Ware shards from allow habitational mound at the centre of this village (Majumder 2017). This discovery indicates that the formation of this village was much earlier than what we usually consider. The area essentially forms an extension

of the Chhotanagpur Plateau region, parceled out from the erstwhile Manbhum district and characterized by a hilly western part and an open upland eastern part (Chakrabarti 1993: 116).

Jainism strongly survived in this village during the early medieval period and we documented good number of Jaina antiquities from different localities of the village. At present a substantial section of the present day population of the village is represented by the Jaina 'Sarak' community. It is interesting to mention here that during the extensive exploration in this village we also documented some remains of Brahmanical sculptures.

We found the archaeological remains in form of the sculptural fragments from the four localities of the present village. Among these localities three are situated inside the village and one find spot is located at the outside of the village near the river bed of Harai.

Locality No 1: Two Jaina images including some fragmented sculptural specimens were found outside the house of Bakreshwar Mahato (**Plate 1**). His house is located at the center of the village and constructed over the ruins of the ancient structural foundation. Both these Jaina images are very small and due to their abraded condition it is very difficult to identify them properly. Among them one is complete and measures 20 x 32 cm (**Plate 2**). This image is made of chlorite stone. The Jina is in *kayotsarga* posture and stands on a full blown lotus placed on a *tri-ratha* pedestal. The top of the back slab is crowned with a tri-liner *chatra*, each smaller than one below. The tri-liner *chatra* is flanked by the divine hands playing on drums and cymbals. The garland bearers are also neatly depicted just below the divine hands playing musical instruments. The Tirthankara is attended by the usual two fly-whisk bearers. Both the sides of the back-slab of this image is without any decoration.

The other Jaina image is half buried and the head of the Tirthankara is missing. However, the back-slab of this image shows the depiction of planetary deities, though only six are visible but it was very difficult to identify the planetary deities individually. Except these two Jaina images some sculptural fragments of Jaina images including a broken memorial stone are also reported from this locality.

Locality No 2: This locality is only 500m. west of the first locality. In front of a school building some Brahmanical and Jaina sculptural remains are kept and preserved in very bad condition (**Plate 3**).

Among the fragmented sculptural specimens, a defaced **Jaina Tirthankara (Plate 6)** image (60 x 45 cm) was also noticed, though the iconographic features of this are completely washed out. However, from the remaining portion it is clearly mentioned that this is a Jaina Tirthankara image. Except these images there are some other fragmented specimens of sculptures belonging to Brahmanical as well as Jaina ideologies.

Locality No 3: This locality is situated in the western side of the village (**Plate 7**). During our exploration we noticed some broken sculptural specimens along with one stone pillar lying under the pipal tree of a modern religious spot known as Sasthi Tala. This religious spot was constructed over the low structural mound. The remains of the earlier brick structure are still visible near this spot (**Plate 8**). Among the broken sculptural remains some noteworthy specimens are a damaged Siva *linga*, small image of seated Jaina Tirthankara (10 x 8 cm), pedestal of a female deity (12 x 20 cm), one damaged *amalaka* etc (**Plate 9**). The undecorated stone pillar (1.50m height) is kept just outside the religious spot (**Plate 10**). The presence of this pillar indicates that there must be a temple near this locality, which survived during the early medieval period and destroyed after the abandonment of the settlement.

Locality No 4: In the eastern side of the village, near the left bank of the river Harai, there is a religious spot known as Dumai Chandi Sthan. This area is 500m away from the village located on the top of the small hillock (**Plate 11**). Though this locality is at present under religious worship but from the nature of the find spot it indicates that this area must have been used as the memorial ground during the early medieval period. We have documented sufficient evidence to support our present assumption. In this locality we have reported good memorial stone pillars and most of them are lying in the ground. We have found in all total 8 stone pillars from this area and these memorial stone can be divided in three types:

- (i) Memorial pillar, top portion decorated with *amlaka* (**Plate 12**).
- (ii) Memorial pillar, top portion decorated with *jhampa simha* (**Plate 13**)
- (iii) Memorial pillar, upper portion decorated with figures (**Plate 14**).

Among these three types of memorial stone pillars, type 1 is more in number than the remaining two types. Five memorial pillars documented from this site belong to type 1. Among these five, the larger one measures 120 cm x 15 cm and the smallest one measures 70 cm x 15 cm. The lower portions (buried portion) of this type of pillars are undressed, the upper portions are square in plan and a projection found horizontally in the central part of the memorial pillar. The top portion of the pillar decorated with stylized *amlaka*. This type of memorial stone may have been used to commemorate persons who had strong religious association with Jainism and Brahmanism like the *archaryas* or *gurus*. Because the decorations of the memorial pillar indicate that it has association with a temple.

We have noticed only two specimens of the second type of memorial pillar. These two pillars measure 80 cm x 25 cm and 28 cm x 25 cm (broken). Both these pillars are rectangular in plan and the top portion is crowned with triumphing lion (*jhampa-singha*). This type of memorial stone may be used to commemorate the person who was involved in warfare.

The remaining one belongs to type three. The top portion of this pillar was broken and the remaining part measures 56 cm x 20 cm. In the central part of this pillar depicts an image of male figure (Siva ?) and female figure (Parvati ?) in very low relief. In this image the divine couple is depicted as seated on a lotus pedestal. The male figure is seated on *lalitasana* posture and female figure sits on his left lap with her right leg hanging down. Due to the abraded condition of this image it is very difficult to study the iconographic features of this image in detail. This type of memorial stone may have been used for the person who was a devotee.

Observation:

In the foregoing pages authors' have tried to analyze the explored data to achieve a clear picture of the archaeological site and its sculptural remains. It is quite clear from the above data that these evidences, ascribable to the Jaina religious idiom, throw light on the growth and development of Jainism and the spread of Jaina settlements, rituals and their relationship with the sculptural art of the said site. It is quite obvious that such concentration of Jaina heritage is not restricted to these particular sites alone. There are some other sites/settlements associated with Jaina ideology in an around the Para block region. It is also worth mentioning here that during our survey in this area we documented some Brahmanical sculptural specimens, mainly Visnu

and Surya images. The presence of these Brahmanical images in the site indicates that though Jainism was very much popular in the area, Brahmanism also simultaneously marked its presence in the religious life of the people of the region.

It has a general tendency among the scholars that the presence of the memorial stones (hero stones) in the site indicates the historical processes of formation of state and society in the tribal-oriented society and presence of memorial stones (hero stones) is a matter of over emphasis and simplicity of historical objectivity. Therefore to extend the theory of interrelationship between hero stones and the processes of formation of state, as highlighted by some authorities as B D Chattopadhyaya in the context of Rajasthan may not be equally applicable for the present study area (Chattopadhyaya 1982:139-49). It is not only in the absence of epigraphic sources but also the nature and context of occurrence that suggest a regional identity, though there are elements in the form of local ruling authorities and subsequent adoption of the tribal modes of belief systems. Gautam Sengupta has also studied the historical identities of hero stones of West Bengal and has suggested that the original purpose and contexts of these specimens have gone into oblivion (Sengupta 1999:77-97). However, in the present context it may be assumed that the erection of the so called memorial stones (hero stones) in the site is not always indicative of the historical processes of formation of state and society. There are some different reasons behind that process and the religious association was not ruled out.

Sculptures briefly described and discussed above on stylistic and iconographic grounds may be assigned to the period between the eleventh and the thirteenth centuries CE. These, including the other stupendous sculptural remains from this district as well as other parts of the Radha region of Bengal, were products created by the fusion of the art idioms of neighboring areas of the Chhotanagpur plateau region and were laid in an essentially local matrix from which came out this distinct center of a regional tradition. These newly reported sculptures show some local variation within the district.

The present work thus shows that the western sectors of West Bengal deserve more careful archaeological investigation in order to understand the nature and pattern of distribution of early medieval sites/settlements and of locating the regional cultural and artistic identities as well as the nature of their religious character. The sculptural remains of this site exhibit that it has some regional variation however, the influence of Pala Sena art is also reflected in the sculptural

heritage of Tatgram. So both the school of art were present in a particular area reflect that though the art style restricted its stretch for a particular area but the product of this art style travelled different zones. The regional art style of this area was so strong that dynastic art not influence this style.

This type of present study indicates that micro-regional case studies are expected to throw new light on the nature of linkages witnessed by the different religious orders and art styles within a local matrix, which also help us to reconstruct an overview about the history of the socio-religious character of the region.

Bibliography:

Bloch, T. 1903. *Annual Report of the Archaeological Survey, Bengal Circle, for the Year Ending with April 1903*. Calcutta.

Beglar, J. D. 1878/1966. Report of a Tour Through the Bengal Provinces of Patna, Gaya, Mongir, Bhagalpur, the Santal Pargana, Manbhum, Singhbhum, Birbhum, Bankura, Ranigunj, Burdwan and Hugli in 1872-73. *Report – Archaeological Survey of India*. VIII. Varanasi: Indological Book House.

Chakrabarti, Dilip K. 1993. *Archaeology of Eastern India: Chhotanagpur Plateau and West Bengal*. New Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal Publishers Pvt. Ltd.

Chattopadhyaya, B.D. 1982. Early Memorial Stones of Rajasthan: A Preliminary Analysis of their Inscriptions, in *Memorial Stones: A Study of Origin, Significance and Variety* (Eds. S Settar and G Sontheimer), Dharwad, pp. 139-49.

Majumder, S. 2017. Jaina Remains in Ancient Bengal: A Study in its Archaeology, Art and Iconography, Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis submitted in the University of Calcutta.

Sengupta, G., 1999. Hero Stones of West Bengal: A Preliminary Study. *Journal of Bengal Art*, 4:77-97.

